

Professor of Medicine in Gastroenterology Simran Gupta (she/her)

"Translational breakthroughs demand both patient treatment and innovative, reproducible research."

Bio

After completing her MD and fellowship in gastroenterology, Simran felt a strong pull toward both patient care and clinical research. To build her research skills, she completed a Master's in Clinical Science Investigation, learning the essentials of research design and implementation. She has worked as a physician scientist for the past 15 years, treating diseases of the intestines and performing procedures while conducting research, teaching, writing and reviewing manuscripts and grants. She is also active in committee work and mentors junior researchers in her department. Simran's proactive and passionate attitude spur her on in these tasks and assist her to build strategic partnerships. Her collaborations with government, industry, and private institutions help supplement the grant funds that allow her to move her research program forward.

Above all, Simran wants to positively impact patient care. Investigating research questions that arise from her clinical work, though sometimes challenging, is to her the most effective way to achieve such impact.

Education: MD, Gastroenterology, MS, Clinical Investigation

Years of experience: 15

Work location: Lab, clinic, teaching spaces, office. Occasional remote work on her laptop

Goals

- Build an effective professional network and research team to enable productivity
- Increase efficiencies in research
- Increase publications, grants, and clinical practice
- Continue to build her knowledge in compliance and dissemination
- Become an editor of a journal

Software attitude & use

- Open to new tools and approaches
- Driven to understand the research design and data analysis plans for her studies, even as she teams with others in their creation
- General: Microsoft Office Suite and Google Workspace
- Collaboration: citation management software, Box, Zoom
- Specialized resources: funder websites, ClinicalTrials.gov, REDCap, PubMed, the Enterprise Data Warehouse and electronic medical records

Outputs

- Articles/manuscripts, generally over 10 per year
- Conference presentations
- Class lectures and materials
- Reviews manuscripts

Pain Points

- Highly demanding job; difficult to find work/life balance
- Waning federal funding, constant search for more grant funds
- Lack of sufficient biostatistical knowledge to conduct her own analyses, requiring partnerships entailing exchange of complex ideas across different domains

Motivators

- Directly impact patient care through her research, either via breakthroughs or improving best practices
- Engineers her own success by constantly seeking funding to explore questions that arise in the course of her clinical work
- Disseminate her findings widely
- Mentor and train early career researchers in research processes

Wants/Needs

- Leadership sympathetic to the challenges of physician scientists
- Effective infrastructure for communication between mentors, researchers, technology experts and entrepreneurs
- Control and understanding of the entire research process even when tasks are delegated
- More efficiency in patient data acquisition (for both treatment and research), documentation, EMR and EDW software
- Quicker response times from administration and fewer regulatory and procedural barriers for study initiation

Professional Development

Department supports continuing medical education credits

Journals are a primary source of information

Mentorship has been crucial to her career, and she is proud to give back as a mentor

Needs departmental support for her own conference travel and for mentees presenting at conferences